

A SNAKE BITE CASE WITH EXTREMELY ELEVATED INTERNATIONAL NORMALIZED RATIO (INR)

Keywords

Snakebite,
INR,
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ABSTRACT

International Normalized Ratio (INR), is a standard unit used to report the result of a prothrombin time (PT) and primarily used to diagnose and manage bleeding diathesis, liver diseases, and monitoring people being treated with warfarin (an anti-clotting treatment). In this report, we described a rare snakebite case with high INR levels.

INTRODUCTION

Snakebite cases are rare. The most common local complications are edema and ecchymosis. The most common systemic complication is nausea, vomiting and altered blood pressure. The incidence of snake bites which have a high INR value is rare¹.

CASE

A 65-year-old male patient was admitted to emergency department three hour after having bitten on the left arm. The patient was hospitalized. The vital signs of the patient were within normal limits. Blood pressure was 110/80 mmHg, heart rate was 84 beats per minute and respiratory rate was 16 breaths/min. Physical examination revealed a slightly tender, bluish-red ecchymosis of 4-5 cm in diameter and mild edema on the bite area. His initial PT-INR value 16,2 (normal range, 0,8 - 1,2) and aPTT was 58.6 s. Other biochemical and hematological parameters were within normal limits. One-unit fresh frozen plasma (FFP) and 14 flacon snake antivenom/250 cc isotonic saline (Equine, European Institute of Immunology, Croatia) were given at four hour interval together with fluid replacement therapy (isotonic saline solution, 0.9%). Consecutive INR values were normalized during two-day follow-up (Table 1 and Figure 1). No spontaneous bleeding or any negative outcome was observed. The patient was discharged with suggestions.

DISCUSSION

Snake venom includes several toxins such as hematoxins, neurotoxins and hemolytic factors and can cause mild local symptoms, systemic complications and death. Viperidae is the most common venomous snakes in Türkiye and have mainly two toxins, hematoxin and neurotoxin¹. Although they show mild local and systemic effects such as edema, ecchymosis, nausea, vomiting they can also lead to severe anemia, bleeding diathesis and necrosis^{2,3}. INR (International Normalized Ratio), is a standard unit used to report the result of a prothrombin time (PT) and primarily used to diagnose and manage bleeding diathesis, liver diseases, and monitoring people being treated with warfarin (an anti-clotting treatment). The incidence of snake bites which have a high INR value is rare.

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CONCLUSION

In conclusion, higher INR values can be observed in snakebite cases and cause bleeding diathesis. Therefore, PT-INR and aPTT tests have vital importance in diagnosis and monitoring of these patients and early anti-venom therapy prevents the development of complications.

Table 1. Coagulation parameters of the patient

Day	Hour	PT-INR	PT (s)	aPTT (s)
1.gün	00:21	16,21	119,6	58,6
1.gün	01:07	12,45	97	57,6
1.gün	19:20	1,27	15,8	27,3
2.gün	00:39	1,18	14,9	29
2.gün	06:36	1,07	13,8	25

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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REFERENCES

1. Karakus A, Kuvandık G. The Case with Hematuria Developing After Snake Bite. *Firat Med J* 2016; 21(4): 229-230.
2. Karakus A, Zeren C, Celik MM, et al. A 5-year retrospective evaluation of snakebite cases in Hatay, Turkey. *Toxicol Ind Health* 2015; 31: 188-92.
3. Şahan M, Taşın V, Karakuş A, Özcan O, Eryiğit U, Kuvandık G. Evaluation of patients with snakebite who presented to the emergency department: 132 cases. *Turkish Journal of Trauma & Emergency Surgery*. 2016;22(4):333-337

Figure 1. INR values of the patients during medical therapy